

ENGINEERING GRAPHICS AND COMPUTERIZATION

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Abstract: Engineering graphics, design important from the parts one is considered and computerization, these technologies, engineering in the field important tasks in execution help gives, for example, design and prototypes work release, presentations make up, and engineering protests more reliable and stored to do Engineering graphics and computerization, engineering in the field new technologies and new approaches in getting important place occupies They are education and teaching because it is important in the field they are new programs learning and them teaching for is used. This topic is new technologies learning, independent workers preparation and engineering in the field high to the results in reaching help gives

Key words: Graphics, technology, design, computerization, engineering, prototypes, programs, new technologies

INTRODUCTORY PART

Engineering field of design important from the parts one is considered This field, engineers and designers for new approaches and opportunities take coming out Of these main the reason is engineering graphics and computerization is engineering in the field independent practices and design systems for very important technologies being remains Engineering graphics, design procedures, presentations structure, and product of creation more to keep teaches. Computerization while engineers and designers for engineering processes more to automation help gives That's two technology, engineering in the field information exchange increases and new technologies in learning is used. In this thesis, engineering graphics and computerization of technologies mutually the effect of their use fields, and engineering in the field new changes in getting own duties about is spoken. Engineering graphics and computerization field, design and engineering more good organize reach, another in the fields application and technological changes acceptance to do for to the hand is taken. These technologies engineers, designers and presenters for important being remains because they are new approaches, new opportunities and independent the work get opportunities take to issue help gives

Main goal: Engineering graphics and computerization, engineering in the field practices more storage and new approaches to receive the goal does They are design and engineering processes new technologies and computers using more efficient and reliable to do they provide.

Main tasks: Education and teaching, Engineering graphics and computerization, engineers and designers for programs, program tools learning and them done in raising help gives They are Create technologies and engineering graphics textbooks preparation own into takes

Design and presentations Structure: Engineering graphics, presentations, model creation and design processes in storage is used. This is the design another in the fields application more efficient does and each the step coordination increases.

Engineering protests automation: computerization, engineering protests automation, automated construction and work release processes own into takes This is variability and work more reliable to do enable creates

new Technologies study: Engineering graphics and computerization, engineers for new technologies in learning and themselves new approaches in preparation help gives They are new computer programs to teach and them done in raising own into takes

Independent workers training: These technologies engineering in the field independent workers as to creations help gives Engineers, designers and presenters new approaches and opportunities in finding their own in the fields independent workers being outputs can Engineering graphics and computerization, design, design processes storage, engineering protests automation, and new approaches in getting help in giving important roles own into takes They are engineers and designers for new technologies learning and them done increase more efficient and easy the way opens.

Summary:

Engineering graphics and computerization, engineering in the field design, presentations structure, and engineering protests new technologies using more efficient to do for important technologies. They are design and engineering protests in learning, presentations in construction, engineering protests in automation, and new approaches in getting important tasks in execution help gives Engineering graphics and computerization, education and teaching in the field programs structure and them in teaching is used. These technologies engineers, designers, and presenters for is important because they are design and engineering protests more good save, work automation, new technologies learning and them done increase enable take in release help gives Engineering field computerization using more efficient and reliable it becomes.

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